

Supplementary material 2. Data collection form

Data collection form

Intervention review – RCTs and non-RCTs

Review title or ID

Study ID (*surname of first author and year first full report of study was published e.g. Smith 2001*)

General Information

1. Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	
2. Name/ID of person extracting data	
3. Study funding source (<i>including role of funders</i>)	

Eligibility

Study Characteristics	Review Inclusion Criteria	Yes/ No / Unclear	Location in text
4. Type of study	Randomised trial		
	Non-randomised trial		
5. Participants			
6. Types of Exposure			
7. Types of outcome measures			
8. Decision:			
9. Reason for exclusion			

DO NOT PROCEED IF STUDY EXCLUDED FROM REVIEW

Population and setting

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each group (i.e. intervention and controls) if available</i>	Location in text <i>(pg & ¶/fig/table)</i>
10. Population description <i>(from which study participants are drawn)</i>		
11. Setting <i>(including location and social context)</i>		
12. Inclusion criteria		
13. Exclusion criteria		

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Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text (pg & ¶/fig/table)
14. Aim of study		
15. Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)		
16. Start date		
17. End date		
18. Duration of participation (from recruitment to last follow-up)		

Participants

Provide overall data and, if available, comparative data for each intervention or comparison group. Add as many rows as needed

Demographics	Total		Group 1		Group 2	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Age						
Male						
Female						
Type of cancer						
Other important demographics						
Other treatment						

Outcomes

Copy and paste table for each outcome.

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text
19. Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)		
20. Person measuring/reporting		
21. Is outcome/tool validated?	Yes/No/Unclear	

Results

Copy and paste the appropriate table for each outcome, including additional tables for each time point and subgroup as required.

For randomised or non-randomised trial - Dichotomous outcome

	Description as stated in report/paper				Location in text
22. Comparison					
23. Outcome					
24. Subgroup					
25. Results Note whether: post-intervention OR change from baseline And whether Adjusted OR Unadjusted	Intervention		Comparison		
	No. events	No. participants	No. events	No. participants	
26. Baseline data	Intervention		Comparison		

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	Description as stated in report/paper				Location in text
	No. events	No. participants	No. events	No. participants	
27. Statistical methods used and appropriateness of these methods					

Other information

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text
28. Key conclusions of study authors		